

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D1.4

Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in marketing and data

Additional material to Appendix 6

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***Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing
biodiversity, including SMART indexes of
agrobiodiversity use in marketing, and data***

NUCs Value Chain Expert Workshop: A step towards “participatory modelling”

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1. Introduction

1.1 What is the DIVINFOOD Project?

The context for the development and implementation of the DIVINFOOD project (Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food) is one of rapid decline of biodiversity, both globally and also in Europe. The current heavy reliance on a small number of varieties is a threat to food security and deprives consumers of the nutritional quality of other species. Currently, small-scale producers and processors offer local food products valuing neglected and under-utilised species (NUCs) in short chains, thus helping to both reverse the decline in biodiversity and meet this demand. However, they face many challenges, from insufficient availability of suitable varieties to difficulty in developing viable business models.

In light of these challenges, the overall objective of the project is to contribute to reversing the agrobiodiversity decline by producing knowledge and tools to support farmers and small-scale processors to develop short- and mid-tier supply chains which value NUCs and meet consumer expectations of local, healthy, plant-based food. DIVINFOOD focuses on legumes and minor cereals, whose use in short and mid-tier chains is increasing, and whose potential for health and agroecology is high. The production of knowledge and tools, from breeding to marketing, involves citizen-consumers and relies on 9 living labs (LLs) gathering all concerned stakeholders from the 7 partner countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland).

1.2 Objective: Valuing consumer-producer interactions

DIVINFOOD uses an approach that considers all the activities that occur along the value chain of the NUC – from seed to plate - with a view to valorise NUCs and ultimately increase their purchase and consumption. The first Work Package (WP) of the project begins with a focus on consumers and food environments so as to better “guide” or inspire the valorisation process along the whole NUC value chain. Its work is founded on the assumption that there is a knowledge (and practice) gap with respect to the mechanisms, networks and physical infrastructure (i.e., food environments

Key Terms:

Neglected and Under-Utilised Crop (NUC)

“NUCs are domesticated plant species that have been cultivated or consumed as food throughout human history but have been reduced in importance over time...with many of them actually disappearing.” (da Silva J., FAO, 2012).

Food environment

“Food environments are the physical, economic, political and socio-cultural contexts in which people engage with the food system to make their decisions about acquiring, preparing and consuming food.” (www.eph.org). A short video on the concept: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5cUaro1gUcl>

Food Value Chain

“A food value chain consists of all the stakeholders who participate in the coordinated production and valueadding activities that are needed to make food products” (FAO 2014) <https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en?details=13953E>

(Downs et al, 2020)) that link the production and consumption ends of the value chain. It is for this reason that one of the objectives of WP1 is to better understand how to influence both “engaged” and “regular” consumers in the valuing of agrobiodiversity, and what role the food retail environment plays in this respect.

Task 1.2, in particular, focuses on analysing NUCs-based products’ value in food environments by drawing on an extensive collection of primary data in the 7 countries involved in the DIVINFOOD project. The specific objectives of this Task are to:

- Analyse food environments in partnering EU countries, focusing on the external domains (e.g.: value chains, infrastructure, prices, labels).
- Analyse, based on examples, how NUCs are valued in different short- and mid-tier value chains in different countries. The analysis also includes the regional/national interpretation of NUCs, i.e., which species or varieties are considered as NUCs in each region or country.
- Identify general lessons learned, good practices, methods etc., to increase the relevance/value of NUCs in value chains.

2. Analyse how NUCs are valued in different short- and mid-tier value chains

2.1 Working with Qualitative and Quantitative Data

Beginning in January 2023, the INRAE and AgriKulti Teams began to collect data from the internet (websites, e-sales platforms, Facebook and Instagram) of venders who were selling ancient cereals and minor legumes. We kept a relatively generic definition of the ancient cereals and minor legumes in order to cast a wide net, but we also included specific searches for the 16 NUCs that are covered by the DIVINFOOD project. This purposive sampling resulted in a list of 1272 actors selling these products.

For these 1272 actors, we copied and conducted computer-assisted translation of the public statements of purpose found the “home” page of each actor. We also copied the “about us” justifications of the vision and missions of the actors. These data are used for quantitative socio-lexical analysis using the CorText platform and qualitative analysis of the “values” that are claimed by the actors. This analysis provides us insights into value(s) produced through agrobiodiversity-based markets (cf. Chiffolleau et al. 2024).

Contact information for 1106 of these actors was obtained and they received an email invitation to participate in an online survey (between January and March 2024) that collected more specific information about how their supply chains were organized, the products that were selling, the missions that they pursued, the forms of communication they used and the benefits that they received from selling NUCs.

The descriptive statistics of the 116 completed responses (74 claimed that they sold NUCs) that we received by 11 March 2024 (10,5% response rate) were analysed in order to characterise the database and to provide the first insights into a typology of value chains that value NUCs in Europe. This empirical data was analysed according to a conceptual framework that was developed based key concepts from the literature on value chains.

2.2 Conceptual Framework for Food Chains that Value NUCs

The purpose of this short presentation of key concepts in the literature on value chains is twofold. First, we aim to understand what current types of value chains have already been studied and characterized in the literature. Second, we aim to develop the variables to be used in our typology based on those that have already been studied.

For this purpose, we first identify the range of types of value chains studied in the literature and then present those categories that offer a diversity of pivot points that we can use to develop our own typology of value chains that value NUCs in Europe.

2.2.1 Characteristics of value(s) chains

The term “value chain” was coined by Michael Porter (1985) as a management tool that could help firms first to identify and then exploit their competitive advantage within an industry, then to “create shared value” among supply chain actors (Porter and Kramer 2011). About 10 years ago, the concept of *circuit court* (Chiffolleau 2012) or short food supply chain emerged, where short supply chains are defined as those with few (maximum one) intermediaries between farmers and consumers (Santini et al. 2013). Mid-tier value chains try to capture this middle space where medium-scale farmers, who are too big for direct sales but too small to reach industrial economies of scale, are able to access quality-based markets (Lev and Stevenson 2011). A lot of the work in this area has tried to elaborate how Porter’s (1985) five primary activities of values chains – **Inbound Logistics, Operations, Outbound Logistics, Marketing & Sales and Services** – can be organized differently based on different **combinations of intermediaries**.

In the 1990s, increased attention was focused on the very long value chains that spanned the globe (Gereffi 1994). Questions of concern emerged in this literature about how such long, diverse chains were coordinated and more precisely governed by powerful actors who requested very specific quality compliance through the use of certification (Ponte, Gereffi and Raj-Reichert 2019). Gereffi’s (1994) governance typology – **hierarchy, captive, relational, modular, and market** – inspired a lot of literature to look at how value chains moved beyond actor and product coordination towards governing the production of alternative values like fairness or sustainability (Loconto 2012). A range of values were found to be produced through attempts to govern **qualities** that were tied to a notion of place (origin, local, territory, proximity) (Fleury et al. 2016).

In the 2000s, “green” value chains were introduced as a concept where environmental and social indicators are taken into consideration in determining the sustainability of the supply chain (Carter and Rogers 2008). However, an interesting concept emerged in the 2010s around “values-based food supply chains” that explained how mid-tier chains were beginning to form directly through producers and their supply chain partners to ensure high-quality, diversified products that were fully traceable (Ostrom et al. 2018). Feenstra and Hardesty (2016) clarified three characteristics of these values-based chains that were able to support regional economies: (1) **transparency** in communicating values throughout the supply chain; (2) the ease with which they can **coordinate purchases** from small and mid-scale producers; and (3) the extent to which they provide **fair prices** to farmers versus remaining **competitive** in the marketplace. Building upon van der Ploeg et al.’s (2012) notion of nested markets, a typology has been introduced that qualifies how values define the producer-consumer relations through **information-rich, socio-cultural, diversified or interactive intermediation** (Loconto et al. 2018).

2.3 Value(s) Chains Typology

The literature cited in the previous section suggests that there are a number of characteristics of food chains that value NUCs (FCVNs) that need to be taken into consideration in analysis. We present them here as the variables that are used to distinguish between different types of value chains. For each variable, we define the variable and how it manifests differently in the empirical data. We define how this variable is operationalised for our value chain typology. We also include the hypothesis to test with this variable.

Variable	Definition	Operationalisation	Hypothesis
Actor Role	Category based on the declared "commercial activity".	Farmer (initiatives that have declared a "food production activity", regardless of the other declared activities); Intermediary (initiatives that have "a role of making the link" between farmers and consumers, including online platforms, CSA); Processor (Baker, miller, processor without an "agricultural production activity"); Shop (initiative's that are in charge of a "physical" sales outlet); Other (Activities limited to one or few such as Research, Education, Inputs/seeds production, Advertising/marketing/promotion)	FCVNs will have a higher number of primary activities carried out by one single actor.
Certification	Qualities guaranteed; Types of certification	Guaranteed Qualities: Taste, Color, Organic, Tradition, Other, Size, Place/origin, Vegan, Nutrition benefits, Ecosystem services, Easy to cook/process, Known recipes, Medical properties, Psychedelic properties, Religion. Weight loss Types of Certification: Third party certification, Participatory guarantee system, Social control, Consumer feedback. Business-to-business (B2B) verification, Self-declaration, Other	FCVNs certify origin and environmental qualities. FCVNs are not using alternative certifications.
Competition	% share of activity is NUCs; Competitive market	NUCs represent % share Consumer prices and margins for selling NUCs : Higher, Lower, The same	FCVNs are not working in a highly competitive market

		Level of competition: Low, Medium, High, No competition, Don't know if competition	
Intermediation	Number and Type of intermediaries	Diversified, Information-rich, Interactive, Socio-cultural	FCVNs tend to use information-rich intermediation
Maturity of the enterprise	The date of foundation ranges from 1819 to 2023	Traditional (founded before 2000), Mature (founded between 2000-2010), Young (founded between 2010-2020), Post-Covid (founded since 2021)	FCVNs are more likely to be young enterprises
Mission-driven	Number and Type of missions	Four groups of mission: Health, Nature, Local economy, Nutrition Number of missions: 0-13	FCVNs have more than one mission
Origin of supply	Origin of NUCs	Same municipality Same region Same country Same continent Outside Europe	FCVNs have a diversified sourcing strategy
Product specialisation	Category of NUC	Cereals vs. Legumes	FCVNs are selling a wide diversity of products.
Coordination	Type of supply contract	Own producer 1 time sale Auction Annual contract Long-term contract Other	FCVNs are typically supplying their own production to their sales
Transparency	Qualities Promoted; Communication channels	Four groups of qualities: Health, Nature, Local economy, Eating (diets, gastronomy) Number of qualities: 0-8 1 - 2 means of communication 3 - 4 means of communication More than 5 means of communication No active promotion of NUCS	FCVNs actively promote NUCs and Qualities online
Vision of NUCs' value	Benefits of NUC	Cultural Social Economic Environmental Political Other	FCVNs claim economic benefits from NUCs sales.

2.4 Draft Typology

The purpose of this typology is to differentiate the variety of ways that agrobiodiversity is valued in the short and mid-tier value chains.

Based on a first analysis of 71 initiatives in 2021, three types of short- and mid-tier chains were identified (Loconto and Garrido-Garza 2021). Following a specific empirical focus on neglected and underutilized crops (NUCs), we further clarified and expanded these types of short- and mid-tier chains. The majority of the initiatives are young, in that they were founded starting in 2010.

The four ideal type value chains presented below are distinguished by the role played by the key driver of the initiative. Additional differences among the analysed variables are used to clarify the following four types:

Farm focused value chains: Driven by producers who are mainly selling their own products, these value chains are locally sourced, mostly specialised in cereals and do not face serious competition in their sale of NUCs. The greatest benefits for selling NUCs are the environmental benefits.

Market quality value chains: Driven by intermediaries, specifically online platforms, these chains value high quality products that are sought after by consumers. Long-term contracts with farmers ensure mid-tier supply chains that can deliver the same consumer prices and sales margins for NUCs when compared to similar conventional products. There is low competition in this market and the benefits for selling NUCs go beyond the environmental benefits to produce social and economic benefits.

Collective Market value chains: Driven by hybrid intermediaries (i.e., processors, restaurants and traders who are often also producing what is sold), these value chains are characterised by collaborative efforts among value chain actors. Annual and long-term contracts ensure continued collaboration and consumer feedback among suppliers who are not necessarily local. While a clear social mission is not articulated, the intermediation in these chains promote a wider range of issues and claim cultural benefits, in addition to environmental benefits, from the sale NUCs.

Diversified value chains: Driven by shops that have typically one physical location (in addition to an online presence), these value chains are highly diversified across all of the criteria. They rely mainly upon indirect supply and one-time sales to ensure that a wide variety of NUCs and values are traded. Facing little to no competition for NUCs, these shops have higher consumer prices but the same profit margins when compared to similar conventional products.

	Farm Focused	Market Quality	Collective Market	Diversified options
Actor role	Producer	Online platform	Producer, Processor, Restaurant	Shop
Certification	Third-party certification	Consumer feedback, self-declaration	Consumer feedback, Third-party certification	Third-party certification, self-declaration, self-control, consumer feedback
Competition	Higher consumer prices, Same margins, no competition	Same consumer prices, margins and low competition	Same consumer prices, slightly lower margins, Medium competition	Higher consumer prices, same profit margins, No competition
Coordination	Own production, 1 time sales	Long-term contract	Annual and Long-term contracts	1 time sales, indirect supply
Intermediation	Information-rich, Socio-cultural	Diversified	Interactive, Socio-cultural	Diversified
Maturity of the enterprise	Young, Traditional	Young	Young	Young
Mission-driven	No social mission (but environmental concern)	Median 4 social missions (Unsustainability, Injustice)	No clear social mission (but Unsustainable production and consumption)	More than 5 social missions (Mainly environmental)
Origin of supply	Same municipality, multiple origins	Same region, same country	Multiple origins (but mostly same country)	All origins (but mostly regional)
Product specialisation	Highly specialised in cereals	Selling both cereals and legumes	Mixed cereals/legumes	Mostly cereals and a range of cereals/legumes
Transparency (Online and word of mouth)	Organic, Place origin	Organic, Place origin	Organic, Place origin, Taste, Nutritional benefits, Ecosystem services	Organic, Place origin, Taste
Vision of NUCs' value	Environment	Environment, Socio-economic	Environment, Cultural	Balanced values

3. Questions for discussion

- 1) Conceptual linkages:
 - a. Are the value chain dynamics captured?
- 2) Clarification of the categories:
 - a. Are there some categories that are not clearly defined or could be better defined?
- 3) Distinctiveness:
 - a. Are the presented value chains distinctive enough to be considered discrete types?
- 4) Empirical examples:
 - a. Does the typology describe initiatives that you are familiar with?
- 5) What's missing?

Quadro concettuale

La tipologia indicata, include tutte le dinamiche delle filiere?

competizione tra NUCs e prodotti convenzionali (non-NUCs)

Aggiungerei il tema cooperativo: common campaign

Chiarimento delle categorie

Tutte le categorie sono specificate? Alcune, di esse, sono migliorabili?

Market quality value chains / Collective Market value chains
The name of these 2 categories should be better distinguished.

Supermarket chiana/ mainstream channels

dimensione collettiva/ collaborativa della filiera anche nelle altre tipologie di filiera (non solo market value chains)

Clarify how the price comparison is done

Caratteristica distintiva

Le quattro filiere tipiche presentate sono sufficientemente distinte l'una dall'altra?

Esempi empirici

La tipologia descrive delle iniziative che sono simili a quelle già operative in Italia/Svizzera?

Farm that sells partly on farm, in an urban coop, and to an SM.

Edicole in crisi- uso della logistica per vendere prodotti trasformati- edicola km 0

Che cosa manca?

Conceptual linkages

Are the value chain dynamics captured?

Clarification of the categories

Are there some categories that are not clearly defined or could be better defined?

market quality is not mission-driven perhaps? While diversified markets

Duration of enterprises

Distinctiveness

Are the presented value chains distinctive enough to be considered discrete types?

There are overlaps between the categories

examples are broader than the categories themselves

not a clear distinction between Market quality and the Diversified

Empirical Examples

Does the typology describe initiatives that you are familiar with?

Some examples fit into more than one category

supermarkets beginning to work with MUCs in Denmark and Portugal
maybe market quality?
maybe diversity oriented?

Working with nudging inside the stores - buy us + pulses in bowls experimenting with mixing

selling in bulk - no packaging, no waste shops

Cooking Lab - promoting pulses, not selling - where does it fit?

do non-profits/NGOs fit into the categories?

What's missing?

incentives or funding of these enterprises?

What about NGOs? Are they included in this typology?

in-store nudging

Linkage with the year of pulses?

financial sustainability of enterprises

Stability of market/ resilience of enterprise?

